

METALLIC FILLER POWDERS TO IMPROVE ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELDING OF FRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

The transparency of FRP to electromagnetic interference is a problem in many aerospace applications. Metallic powders have been added to laminates to improve the Electromagnetic Shielding Effectiveness (EMSE). This creates laminates with shielding properties equal to, or better than a, similar thickness aluminium plate. Tensile properties and blast response were also affected.

Keywords: Electromagnetic Shielding, FRP, metallic fillers.

INTRODUCTION

Comparatively little research has been undertaken regarding new electromagnetic shielding materials in the past ten years [1]. Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite materials have, however, been identified in recent years as being the desired choice for the replacement of orthodox metallic alloys in many aerospace applications. One of the chief obstacles is the inherent lack of electromagnetic shielding capabilities possessed in most FRP composite materials. Modern aircraft are essentially “fly-by-wire” systems, making them potentially very sensitive to EM interference. Little advancement in shielding has been made since the 1990’s [1] possibly due to the perception that shielding adds mass and offers no value other than EM protection to the electronic device [1].

While it is true that some EMI can simply result in minor static on the aircraft pilot’s headphone, the result can be as severe as a complete shut-down of onboard avionics [2]. This could lead to possible loss of control of the aircraft and possible loss of life. When defining the performance of a shielding material, the term often quoted is shielding effectiveness (EMSE). This value, obtained in decibels, provides an indication of the quality of shielding a material possesses. The frequency range specified for this work ranged from 800MHz to 5GHz, regarded as “far-field” [3, 8].

The requirement of this work was to develop good EMI shielding from a high strength fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite. The current approach is to use conductive meshes as a layer in the laminate. By adding metallic filler powders to the resin, it was possible to obtain EMSE values similar to an equivalent thickness Aluminium plate. The impact of these approaches (metallic fillers and/or metallic meshes) on the mechanical strength was then investigated. Two cases were considered: the normal

operational quasi-static loading and an extreme explosive blast loading case. With these composite materials possibly being used in the design and manufacture of primary structures in the aircraft industry, there is increasing concern relating to the possibility of these materials being subjected to blast loading. There are, however, a limited number of research articles that discuss the response of composite materials to air-blast loading. A preliminary study was thus performed to look at the affect if any of the filler materials and on the response of the FRP composite to a nearby explosive detonation.

ELECTROMAGNETIC SHIELDING

EMI in aircraft may be classified into three sub-classes, which are: on-board systems, passenger carry-on devices, and externally generated EMI [4]. Passenger carry-on devices include portable electronic devices that can transmit and receive frequencies, compact disc players and computers. Anyone who has flown on-board an aircraft has been cautioned against use of these devices during flight. Externally-generated EMI refers to disturbances caused by external sources such as lightning strike, high intensity radio frequency energy (HIRF) and electromagnetic pulses (EMP) [4].

The basis for electromagnetic shielding against these three types is attained from a classical structure referred to as a “Faraday cage”. This structure, which contains an electrically conductive outer layer, provides fundamental protection for electronic equipment that is to be protected from electric fields. The external electric field of the structure redistributes electrons such that the total electric field within the enclosure is always zero [5].

Shielding of electromagnetic radiation can be achieved by means of reflection, absorption and multiple reflections. Figure 1 describes the interaction of electromagnetic waves with a particular shielding medium.

Figure 1: The possible interactions of EM radiation with a material.

The primary mechanism for shielding in highly electrically conductive structures, such as metals, is reflection. Reflection relies on the presence of mobile charge carriers within the material, such as electrons. Therefore, the shielding materials tend to be electrically conductive, although this is not a prerequisite requirement for shielding [6]. Electrical conduction requires connectivity in the conduction path, whereas shielding does not [6]. Thus, a high degree of electrical conductivity is not typically a requirement for shielding, but shielding has been found to be enhanced by connectivity [7]. Reflection loss is a function of the ratio of conductivity to permeability σ_r/μ_r , and reflection losses decrease with increasing EM frequency [6, 7]. (σ_r describes the

conductivity of a material relative to copper, and μ_r describes the permeability of a material relative to copper).

The secondary mechanism for shielding in these structures is absorption. Significant absorption of the EM waves by the shield requires electric and / or magnetic dipoles within the shield material. Absorption is also a function of σ_r/μ_r , and absorption increases with increasing frequency. Absorption is also proportional to shield thickness [6, 7].

The third mechanism for shielding is multiple reflections. Multiple wave reflections take place at surfaces or interfaces within the shield. This mechanism requires the presence of large surface areas or interfaces within the shield [6, 7].

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Composite laminates with increasing quantities of metallic filler powders, and layers of aluminium mesh were fabricated. The focus was to determine if any general trends with increasing filler loading could be observed in mechanical, electrical and EMSE properties of the composites. Thus aluminium powder; copper powder; and a combination of both powders; were introduced into the matrix materials in 7.5% and 15% filler loadings. It was also decided that layers of aluminium mesh fabrics (Alumesh 401) would be also be investigated as this the current approach for ensuring SE and electrical conductivity in FRP structures.

The panels were made at the University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN) in Durban, South Africa. The results detailed here are for a 12K plain weave carbon fibre fabric with an areal weight of approximately 200g/m^2 with LR20 epoxy resin and LH281 hardener. These laminates were made by hand lay-up and vacuum bagging of 10 layers. Copper and / or aluminium fillers were added to the resin prior to laminating, or layers of Alumesh 401 were added to the surface of the laminate as required. These panels were sent for EMSE testing and subsequently cut into specimens for mechanical testing. The mechanical testing included quasi-static tensile and small scale air blast loading tests performed at UKZN and the University of Cape Town (UCT) respectively.

SE Testing

Figure 2: The Scientific Atlanta 5754 compact antenna range test set-up at the University of Pretoria, South Africa [8]

Far-field SE measurements were obtained by use of a Scientific Atlanta compact range antennae setup, with a Hewlett Packer 8510C network analyzer, at the University of Pretoria, South Africa. Testing equipment of this type is referred to as a “two-port network system” [2]. The sample sizes were 300 x 300mm squares and were measured relative to an Aluminium plate of similar thickness. The results were then normalised to the Aluminium plate so that the results could easily be presented graphically. A photograph of the University of Pretoria test set up is shown in figure 2.

Mechanical Testing

The focus of these mechanical tests was to determine if the addition of filler metal and / or layers of Alumesh 401 affected the strength and stiffness of the laminates when compared to un-filled laminates. Initial tensile and bend testing was undertaken on the panels at UKZN using an Instron 5500R universal testing machine. The tests were performed in accordance with ASTM 638-02a and ASTM 69272-02 respectively. A further set of bend tests was performed at UCT on a Zwick 94851, with these bend tests performed in accordance with ASTM D7264M-07.

Blast tests

Figure 3: Photograph of experimental arrangement

Square composite panels with a side length of 150 mm were clamped between two frames, leaving a circular area (diameter 90 mm) to be exposed to the blast loading. A 180 mm long tube, inside diameter 90 mm, was screwed onto the front clamping frame and the rear frame had a hole machined to 90 mm diameter. The frames were mounted to a ballistic pendulum which was used to provide an estimate of the impulse imparted to the panel. This arrangement is similar to that used by Jacob *et al* [9] for metal specimens and Yahya *et al* [10] for composite panels. A photograph of the experimental arrangement is shown in Figure 3. The blast loading was generated by detonating 20

mm diameter discs of PE4 plastic explosive at the open end of the tube. The blast wave was directed down the tube towards the panel resulting in a spatial distribution that was approximately uniform [9]. Three panels of each configuration were tested using different masses of PE4 to vary the impulse. The aim of the experiments was to determine if the addition of metal filler particles, or the presence of Alumesh 401, had any influence on the blast response of the composites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EMSE testing

The results obtained from actual SE testing show that the carbon fibre laminates with filler and / or Alumesh are suitable for some shielding purposes. The laminates without filler displayed inherent capabilities, and inclusion of fillers enhanced this shielding further. In some tests, at certain frequencies, the composite samples were found to display better shielding properties than the aluminium plate itself. However, this could be due to diffraction occurring at some frequencies.

It was noted that there was an increase in SE when two Alumesh 401 layers were used instead of one. The increase in SE, is however probably not significant enough to incur the cost and mass penalties of using two layers in practice. Figures 4 and 5 below show the results of EMSE testing on the 12K woven carbon fibre epoxy laminates. Table 1 then shows the results of the averaged values of SE over the frequency range tested.

Figure 4: Far Field EMSE results for woven CF Epoxy laminates with increasing Cu and Al fillers relative to a 3mm Aluminium plate.

Figure 5: Far Field EMSE results for woven CF Epoxy laminates with increasing layers of Aluminium mesh relative to a 3mm Aluminium plate.

Table 1: Averaged (across the 750-5000MHz frequency range) results of SE for woven CF Epoxy laminates with Al and Cu fillers or Alumesch 401 layers.

Material	Average SE (dB)	Normalized SE
Aluminium base	20.01	1
Woven 12 K carbon fibre / epoxy, 0% filler	20.44	1.0214
Woven 12 K carbon fibre / epoxy, 7.5% Al and Cu filler	20.28	1.0136
Woven 12 K carbon fibre / epoxy, 15% Al and Cu filler	20.41	1.0199
Woven 12 K carbon fibre / epoxy, 1 Alumesch 401 layer	20.38	1.0184
Woven 12 K carbon fibre / epoxy, 2 Alumesch 401 layers	21.12	1.0558

Mechanical Testing

The results discussed here are the initial tensile tests performed at UKZN. The tensile strength of the 12K woven samples ranged from 820 MPa for samples without filler down to 595 MPa for samples with 15% mixture of aluminium and copper powder. The

elastic modulus was found to decrease quite significantly, from 73 GPa without filler to as low as 45 GPa with 7.5% copper powder. Failure was characterised by complete fracture of the material perpendicular to the gauge length. These results can be seen in figures 6 and 7.

Figure 6 Tensile strength - Woven CF Epoxy samples with added filler powders and / or mesh layers.

Figure 7 Elastic Modulus – Woven CF Epoxy samples with added filler powders and / or mesh layers.

Blast tests

A summary of the blast test results is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Blast test results

Panel Designation	Total thickness (mm)	Impulse (Ns)	Mid-point displacement (mm)		% Boundary tearing	Failure Modes ¹
			Back face	Front face		
<i>Woven CF/epoxy, no filler</i>						
K1	1.93	7.9	1.25	2.01	20	FB, FF
K2	1.93	10.3	15.85	14.83	53	DL,
K3	1.93	9.4	8.33	8.52	32	DL,
<i>Woven CF/epoxy, 7.5 % Aluminium powder filler</i>						
M1	2.41	8.3	4.38	3.79	39	FF,DL,
M2	2.41	9.9	8.13	7.41	49	FF,DL,
M3	2.41	8.1	1.52	0.75	19	FF,DL
<i>Woven CF/epoxy, 15 % Aluminium powder filler</i>						
J1	2.52	9.3	1.39	1.1	35	FF,
J2	2.52	10.5	7.43	6.26	59	FF,
J3	2.52	8.2	0.43	0.09	11	FF, DL
<i>Woven CF/epoxy, 7.5 % Copper powder filler</i>						
N1	2.4	8.2	0.18	0.19	3	FF
N2	2.4	10.4	11.04	6.43	78	DL,FF,
N3	2.4	9.6	3.51	2.65	40	FF, DL,
<i>Woven CF/epoxy, 15 % Copper powder filler</i>						
L1	2.29	9.2	4.66	4.3	29	FF,DL,
L2	2.29	10.4	10.34	10.12	76	FF,DL,
L3	2.29	8.3	1.29	0.39	33	FF,DL
<i>Woven CF/epoxy, unfilled, 2 plies Alumesh 401</i>						
A1	2.42	8.2	1.03	2.59	3	FB
A2	2.42	10.3	8.96	8.09	32	FF,FB
A3	2.42	11.5	17.2	16.46	61	FF,DL,
¹ FB = fibre buckling, FF = fibre fracture, DL = delamination						

All the panels exhibited large inelastic deformations, with displacements ranging from half a plate thickness up to eight plate thicknesses. A graph of front face displacement versus impulse is shown in Figure 8a, and reveals a general trend of increasing displacement with increasing impulse. A graph of percentage boundary tearing versus impulse is shown in Figure 8b. All the panels also exhibited fibre fracture which increased in extent with increasing impulse. Large inelastic deformations were unexpected – work by Yayha et al [10] has shown that other woven carbon fibre /epoxy composites subjected to similar blast loading exhibited little permanent

deformation up to failure, and that fragmentation and shear failure around the boundary were the dominant failure modes. None of the panels tested in the current work failed in shear.

(a) Front face displacement

(b) % boundary tearing

Figure 8 (a) and (b): Graphs of displacement and tearing, respectively, vs impulse

The 12K carbon fibre / epoxy panels with no filler showed the largest permanent displacements for a given impulse, as seen in Figure 8a. From this preliminary study, it appears that the addition of filler metal powder lowers the permanent displacement of the panels for a given impulse. Aluminium filler powder appears to offer more benefit than copper powder, particularly when considering back face displacements. This is evident in Table 2 and illustrated by considering a nominal impulse of 10 Ns - the aluminium filled composites exhibit lower displacements than their copper filled counterparts. There appears to be no discernable influence of filler metal powder upon boundary tearing as shown in Figure 8b, however, panels with two layers of Alumesch 401 consistently exhibited the lowest levels of boundary tearing.

CONCLUSION

The principal of adding metal powders to carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites as a cost effective method of improving the shielding effectiveness has been demonstrated. It has also been shown in this work that there was a slight improvement in SE when metal mesh was used compared with materials with the discontinuous fillers, however, not significantly as to justify the use of metal meshes in carbon fibre composites unless the surfaces are exposed to high current such as lightning strikes. The addition of fillers does negatively impact the tensile strength and modulus, but not significantly more than the addition of metal meshes such as Alumesch 401. Interestingly the addition of filler metal powders does appear to improve the response of the 12 K woven carbon fibre, LR20 / LH281 epoxy laminates to small scale blasts. Further work is planned to

investigate this effect and attempt to understand and quantify these blast test results. Overall it appears that the principal of adding metallic fillers to carbon fibre laminates is a potential alternative to the current aluminium mesh approach of improving the electromagnetic shielding properties of fibre reinforced polymer composites.

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References

1. Schlechter, M; "EMI: Materials and Technologies" - abstract; www.electronics.ca
2. Yang, S et al; "Electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness of carbon nanofiber/LCP composites"; *Composites Part A: Applied science and manufacturing* vol. 36 (2005); 691-697
3. White, DRJ; "Electromagnetic Shielding Materials and Performance"; Don White Consultants, Inc.; USA; 1980
4. Shooman, ML; "A study of occurrence rates of electromagnetic interference (EMI) to aircraft with a focus on HIRF (external) high intensity radiated fields"; NASA Contractor Report 194895; National Aeronautics and Space Administration Langley Research Center, Hampton, Virginia; 1994
5. Young H.D and Freedman R.A. "Sears and Zemansky's University Physics". 10th international edition, Addison-Wesley Publishing Company, 2000
6. Yang, S et al; "Electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness of carbon nanofiber/LCP composites"; *Composites Part A: Applied science and manufacturing* vol. 36 (2005); 691-697
7. Chung, DDL; "Electromagnetic interference shielding effectiveness of carbon materials"; *Carbon* vol. 39 (2001); 279-285
8. Equipment photo: © Prof. JW Odendaal; University of Pretoria; October 2006
9. N. Jacob, G.N. Nurick and G.S. Langdon, "The effect of stand-off distance on the failure of fully clamped circular mild steel plates subjected to blast loads", *Eng Structures*, 29, pp. 2723-2736, 2007.
10. M.Y. Yahya, W.J. Cantwell, G.S. Langdon, G.N. Nurick, "The blast behaviour of fibre reinforced thermoplastic laminates", *J. Compos Materials*, 42(21), pp. 2275-2297, 2008.